

OVERCOMING DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE TO ADULTS, MULTILINGUAL SETTINGS AND TEACHING TECHNIQUES

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Annotation All living creatures have some means of conveying information to others of their own group, communication being ultimately essential for their survival. Some use vocal noises, others physical movement or facial expression. Many employ a variety of methods. Birds use predominantly vocal signals, but also show their intentions by body movements; animals use vocal noises as well as facial expressions like the baring of teeth; insects use body movements, the most famous of which are the various ‘dances’ of the bees.

Key words: second language acquisition, general English skills, first language, foreign language, ELF, teaching and learning, multicultural, multiethnic, multilingual country, Language Center English classes, English courses, SEEU faculties, methodological strategies, different language, cultural and religious backgrounds, elementary and high school, "teacher-student" system.

Аннотация: Все живые существа имеют некоторые средства передачи информации другим членам своей группы, и общение в конечном итоге имеет важное значение для их выживания. Некоторые используют голосовые шумы, другие - физические движения или выражение лица. Многие используют самые разные методы. Птицы используют преимущественно голосовые сигналы, но также демонстрируют свои намерения движениями тела; животные используют голосовые шумы, а также выражения лица, такие как скалывание зубов; насекомые используют движения тела, наиболее известными из которых являются различные «танцы» пчел.

Ключевые слова: овладение вторым языком, общее знание английского языка, первый язык, иностранный язык, ELF, преподавание и обучение, мультикультурная, многоэтническая, многоязычная страна, курсы английского языка в языковом центре, курсы английского языка, факультеты SEEU, методологические стратегии, другой язык, культурные и религиозные фонны, начальная и средняя школа, система «учитель-ученик».

Difficulty with vocabulary words that have several different meanings, Have you ever come across a word that you knew (as you thought), but which was used in a completely strange way? English vocabulary is especially difficult because many words have many different meanings that can be easily confused. After all, it's not easy to remember many different definitions for each word. For example, let's take the word date. This word can mean: A specified day of the month, A time two people spend with each other romantically, The only way to correctly determine which value is being used is to follow the context. This means that you need to use the surrounding words and sentences to understand which of the definitions of the incomprehensible word is appropriate here.

Even if you don't know the meaning of a difficult word, contextual clues can help you understand it! Can you figure out what the meaning of the word date is in the sentences below? When's the date for the first day of school again? Would you like to go on a date with me? In the first sentence, someone asks what day school starts. This is not a romantic encounter between the two. The first definition fits here.

Being trained, teachers know that there are ways to demonstrate and explain vocabulary or any other linguistic problem by using synonyms, antonyms, gestures, or mime, and using these strategies may help teachers avoid the L1 use in the classes. Even though the Language Center policy is to only use English as a language of instruction, both teachers and students are tempted to use their L1 during the English classes. In this paper, I will discuss using the L1 in the English classes and its role in the process of acquiring the target language.

Literature review, Pros and cons of using the L1 in the English class, EFL teachers, based on their experiences as learners of a foreign language; claim that the mother tongue has a beneficial role in second language acquisition and learning.

Using L1 has a great impact on the EFL learning process. Many scholars claim that learners acquire a second language by using the knowledge they already have of their native language. Implementing this strategy enables them to cope with communication difficulties and interactions. Studies have shown that learners rely on their background experiences and prior knowledge of their native language to acquire a second language. They use structures from their first language that are comparable to the second language transfer forms and meanings while attempting to read, speak or write the second language. Using L1 in EFL classes has been a very debatable question. This question has divided scholars into two groups.

On one hand, there are those who support the use of L1, such as Atkinson (1987), who strongly supports the theory that students' mother tongue shouldn't be completely ignored in the English classes since "the use of L1 can be very effective in terms of the amount of time spent explaining" (Atkinson, 1987:242). On the other hand, there are those who are against the use of L1, claiming that the overuse of L1 restricts the students' exposure to the target language. Among a number of teachers in second language acquisition, there seems to be an increasing conviction that the first language (L1) has a facilitating role in the second language acquisition (Schweer, 1999). Also, Ferrer, (2000) states that a good number of teachers guided from their experiences as learners of a second language claim that the mother tongue has an active and beneficial role in instructed second language acquisition learning. Stern (1992) suggests that L1 and L2 could not be considered apart as he argues that: "the L1-L2 connection is an indisputable fact of life, whether we like it or not the new knowledge is learned on the basis of the previously acquired language" (1992: 282).

In his research, he concludes that excluding the use of L1 will obstruct the comprehension of the target language effectively. The author continues explaining that if the learner lacks comprehension, one will not be able to achieve any success in learning the language; therefore, the author supports the use of L1 when it is considered necessary. Macaro (2005:532) points out that avoiding the L1 increases usage of input modification (e.g. repetition, speaking more slowly, substituting basic words for more complex ones, simplifying syntax, etc.) which is time-consuming as well as makes the teaching boring and less realistic. In line with these facts, Nunan and Lamb (1996) consider that L1 is inevitable during the learning process, particularly at low levels.

English Teaching Techniques, Since the builders of the Tower of Babel spoke different languages, society began to need translators. Interpreters were appreciated everywhere. Until recently, foreign language was more of a hobby than a cruel reality. To know a foreign language meant to be an esthete, to belong to a certain circle, or (the most innocuous option) - to be known as an eccentric. But times are changing.

Any house, as you know, begins with an architectural plan. Now we are less and less frightened by a huge fortress called "Foreign Language", at the top of which a flag (most often British) flies proudly. And, in this case, knowledge of modern teaching methods will serve as this necessary plan. Recently, when the educational technology market is replete with proposals for a wide variety of methods of learning English, the question "What method do you use to teach?" becomes more and more relevant, which indicates an increase in the culture of consumption of intellectual products. A perplexed applicant, student, or businessman (however, also a student) increasingly freezes in front of bookshelves with linguistic literature and media aids or pensively looks through a long list of advertisements. One of the selection criteria is the price, but the main one ... "English in two weeks", "Communicative methods of teaching English", "English with Englishmen in Moscow", "Effective express method", "English at the subconscious level", eventually. So much is new and unknown! And this gives rise to doubts about the results. Can you trust modern technology? Or give preference to well-established "brands" - such as "Bonk", "Eckersley" or "Headway", which are gradually moving into the category of methodological classics?

The fact remains that at the end of the XX century. in Russia there was a "revolution" in the methods of teaching English. Previously, all the priorities without a trace were given to grammar, almost mechanical mastery of vocabulary, reading and literary translation. These are the principles of the "old school", which (to give it its due) still bore fruit, but at what cost? Language acquisition was carried out through long routine work. The tasks were quite monotonous: reading the text, translating, memorizing new words, retelling, and exercises on the text. Sometimes, for the sake of the necessary change of activity, - an essay or dictation, plus phonetic drills as a rest. When priority was given to reading and working on "topics", only one function of the language was realized - the informative one. It is not surprising that only a few people knew the language well: only very purposeful and

hardworking people could master it at a high level. But in terms of grammar proficiency, they could easily compete with Cambridge graduates! True, they received good compensation for their work: the profession of a teacher of a foreign language or a translator was considered very prestigious in our country.

Now, to achieve this still high social status, it also requires a lot of diligence, perseverance and daily work. But what is truly "revolutionary" is that language has become accessible to the majority in one form or another. And the offer is more and more consumer-oriented. Why, for example, would the secretary acquire knowingly unnecessary knowledge about the palatalization of consonants or the actual division of English sentences? A secretary-assistant or manager who has 8-hour, or, as it is now customary to say, "monopoly" office work, is focused on the development of very specific knowledge and skills, that is, on the consumption of a specific segment of the market for educational offers for learning English. A well-known specialist in the field of linguistics and methods of teaching a foreign language S.G. Ter-Minasova rightly notes that recently, language learning has become more functional: "The unprecedented demand demanded an unprecedented supply.

Unexpectedly, foreign language teachers were in the center of public attention: legions of impatient specialists in various fields of science, culture, business, technology and all other areas of human activity demanded immediate teaching of foreign languages as a tool of production. They are not interested in either theory or history of the language - foreign languages, primarily English, they require exclusively functionally, for use in various spheres of society as a means of real communication with people from other countries". With the form of education, the situation has also become noticeably simpler: going to the office, one-on-one classes with a teacher, going home to a student, "weekend" groups, for busy and not so busy, for "pioneers" and retirees. The main question remains to be solved: what are the content of the course, its structure and teaching methods? Who is the author of the proposed material, where was this material developed and by whom was it tested?

Language teaching has acquired an applied character; while earlier it was comparatively abstract and theorized. Even Aristotle brought out the famous triad of teaching ethics, which correlates perfectly with modern requirements: *logos* - the quality of presentation, *pathos* - contact with the audience, *ethos* - attitude towards others. This rule is true for the speaker, and for the actor, and for the teacher of a

foreign language, the role of which also assumes the first two hypostases. The functions of the teacher in the educational process have changed significantly.

Perhaps the most famous representative of the classical methodology of teaching a foreign language is N.A. Bonk. Her English textbooks, written jointly with other authors, have long become classics of the genre and have withstood the competition of recent years. The classical technique is otherwise called fundamental: no one promises that it will be easy, that you will not have to study at home and the teacher's experience will save you from mistakes in pronunciation and grammar. But the reward will be, developing the fortress metaphor, the state of a real local who knows how not to get lost in the labyrinth of the subjunctive mood or the past tense. And further. The fundamental methodology assumes that your favorite question is "why?" That you will not be content with explanations "it should be so", but are ready to plunge into an interesting, complex, and very logical world, whose name is the language system.

The classic approach to learning a foreign language, In this regard, the classical approach to the study of a foreign language has also somewhat transformed, but the unshakable principles of the "classics" of Russian language methods have been preserved. Sometimes they are actively used in schools of other methodological directions. The classic course is aimed at students of different ages and most often involves learning the language "from scratch". The tasks of the teacher include traditional, but important aspects of the formulation of pronunciation, the formation of a grammatical base, the elimination of the psychological and language barriers that impede communication. "Classics" did not change the goals, but the methods, due to the new approach, are already different.

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